

Title of proposal

IEC 61400-15: Assessment of Wind Resource, Energy Yield and site suitability input conditions for wind power plants

Scope:

The scope of this standard is to define a framework for assessment and reporting of the wind resource, energy yield and site suitability input conditions for both onshore and offshore wind power plants. This includes:

1. Definition, measurement, and prediction of the long-term meteorological and wind flow characteristics at the site
2. Integration of the long-term meteorological and wind flow characteristics with wind turbine and balance of plant characteristics to predict net energy yield
3. Characterizing environmental extremes and other relevant plant design drivers
4. Assessing the uncertainty associated with each of these steps
5. Addressing documentation and reporting requirements to help ensure the traceability of the assessment processes

The framework will be defined such that applicable national norms are considered and industry best practices are utilized.

The meteorological and wind flow characteristics addressed in this document relate to wind conditions, where parameters such as wind speed, wind direction, air density or air temperature are included to the extent that they affect the operation and structural integrity of a wind turbine (WTGS) and energy production analysis.

According to IEC 61400-1 and 61400-3 the site specific conditions can be broken down into wind conditions, other environmental conditions, soil conditions, ocean/lake conditions and electrical conditions. All of these site conditions other than site specific wind conditions and related documents are out of scope for this standard.

This standard is framed to complement and support the scope of related IEC 61400 series standards by defining environmental input conditions. It is not intended to supersede the design and suitability requirements presented in those standards. Specific analytical and modeling procedures as described in IEC 61400-1, 61400-2, and 61400-3 are excluded from this scope.